

Disaster Response and Recovery Using Spatial Analysis and Clustering

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ABSTRACT

The aftermath of recent disasters like earthquakes and tsunamis has highlighted the shortcomings of the present disaster response and recovery mechanism. Large amount of random data is generated during and after a disaster. Deriving meaningful insights from this data can help in effective disaster management practices like preparation, response and recovery. In this paper we propose a model that performs spatial analysis and clustering on the real time as well as static data. The various data used for analytics are disaster data, population density, resource information data and social feeds. The Nepal earthquake of 25th April, 2015, is used as a case study example. The output of this model is layered maps and priority clusters. These maps and clusters can help the rescue teams and the disaster victims in the disaster response and recovery process.

Keywords: Layered Map, Weighted Algorithm, Geographic Information System (GIS), Factor Intensity.

INTRODUCTION

Disasters can either be due to human-made or natural causes. Human-made disasters consist of civil disorder, terrorism, war, industrial hazards, power outage, structural collapse, radiation contamination and others. Natural disasters consist of earthquakes, tsunamis and hurricanes. A specific disaster may indirectly cause a secondary disaster.

Disaster Management is the planning, organization and management of resources for dealing with an emergency situation. It is done with respect to preparedness, response and recovery in order to reduce the impact of disasters.^[1] It includes activities to analyze the possibility of a disaster and its impact on life and property. Initial planning is followed by the preparedness phase that focuses on plans to save lives and minimize disaster damage.

Response phase of the disaster management includes post disaster activities like providing emergency assistance for victims, stabilizing the situation and reducing the chances of a secondary damage. Recovery constitutes of the activities that helps in restoring the systems to normalcy. Recovery can either be short term or long term.

Disaster data is generally immense and chaotic. Data Analytics involves processing this data to discover hidden patterns, unknown correlations and trends.^[2] This analysis cannot be used in prevention of disasters like the Nepal earthquake, but it can help in the post-disaster response and recovery operations. It can be used directly and indirectly in reducing casualties. The output of such an analysis can be used by rescue teams for well-organized and effective rescue missions, resource management and allocation. For analysis, various data fields like disaster impact intensity, social news and population density need to be taken into consideration.

Historically, disaster managements programs are planned and

implemented after the disasters have taken place. This has proved to be an inefficient approach. During an actual disaster, it is critical to have the right data, at the right time, displayed in a logical manner, for one to respond appropriately. All phases of emergency management depend on data from static and real time sources. This data has to be gathered, organized, and analyzed to be able to draw some useful conclusions; which can be used to further the response and recovery operations.

In the wake of a disaster, rescue teams are primarily deployed to the high priority regions, based on public knowledge of population count, damage magnitude, public infrastructure and terrain. Sometimes, the primary disaster may trigger an unexpected secondary disaster, thus wreaking more havoc on the population. (An example would be the Japanese tsunami of 2011 triggered by the earthquake. This in turn sabotaged the nuclear power plants causing an even greater disaster)

The geographic information system (GIS) is used to capture topographical data, population, public infrastructure data such as buildings, roadways, railroads etc.^{[3][4]} Sentiment and real time analysis is used to capture the distress feeds and impact intensity graphs.^[5] All this data is then fed into the model which generates responsive maps with priority clusters, based on an internal weighted algorithm. Furthermore, it provides a resource information data bank for the general public. The generated maps and reports are used in dispensing rescue aid and resources to the appropriate regions.

In the recent years there has been an increase in the amount of analytics work that has been done using the disaster data. One of such example is Hurricane Sandy. Hurricane Sandy brought unprecedented disruption to New York City, displacing an eighth of the City's residents, leaving twice that many without power, shutting down the buses and subways, and bringing the

City to a standstill. During the immediate response and the prolonged recovery, analytics were used to manage the City's response.[6]

The ESRI website helps governments, businesses and individuals to positively impact the future through a deeper, geographic understanding.[7] They combine their analytical knowledge with geographic information system (GIS) to create responsible and sustainable solutions to problems at local and global scales.

MODEL DESIGN

For the above stated problems, we have devised a model that takes in static and real time data and performs analysis and uncovers hidden patterns and trends. Static data such as topography, geology, building infrastructures (hospitals, airports, police stations, power plants etc.), sewer and pipeline network, electrical and network grid, population density, country shapefiles are stored in a spatial format.[5] Real time data like social feeds, satellite imagery, impact intensity graphs etc. are fed into the model.

The model given below can be summarized into the following points

- ❖ First we need to find all the cluster direct or indirect factors that affect the impact of a disaster.
- ❖ Impact Probability of each factor needs to be calculated from the past data. Impact Probability is the extent to which the factor will affect the disaster impact.
- ❖ A damage score is calculated, for each location, according to a weighted algorithm.
- ❖ All the data pertaining to the factors are stored in a spatial format. This data is plotted on the map of the disaster struck area.
- ❖ Clusters are formed, based upon the spatial data, using divisive clustering algorithm.
- ❖ Each cluster may contain various locations. Clusters are prioritized based on the sum of the damage scores, calculated in step 3, of the locations within it.

Fig 1: Proposed Model

DATA STUDY

The data from the various factors needs to be collaborated through some weighted formula to get the damage score for a specific location. To calculate damage score of a location the following methodology, explained using an example, will be used. We have taken Kathmandu as an example. The actual impact intensity of Kathmandu is 4.5 on the Richter scale.[8]

Impact Probability of a factor for a specific location is calculated from the past data. The following example shows the calculation of Impact Probability of a factor (twitter feeds) for Kathmandu from past data.[5]

Total number of twitter feeds from Kathmandu during any disaster (T) = 1154.

Number of distress twitter feeds during that disaster (N) = 786.

Probability factor of twitter feeds ($PF1$) = $\frac{N}{T} = \frac{786}{1250} = 0.6288$
 Similarly probability factors (PF) are calculated for all factors from their past data.

Impact Probability ($IP1$) of twitter feeds = $\frac{PF1}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} PF_i} = \frac{0.6288}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} PF_i} = 0.06$.

Similarly Impact Probabilities (IP) are calculated for all factors using the above formula.

Impact Intensity of Kathmandu (II) = 4.5

Factor Intensity of twitter feeds (FI) = $II * IP1 = 4.5 * 0.06 = 0.27$.

Similarly Factor Intensities are calculated for all the factors as shown in Table 1.

Expected Factor-Intensity Added (EFA) for Kathmandu = $\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} FI_i$.

Expected Factor-Intensity Added (EFA) for a specific location will be calculated using the given method as shown in Table 1.

Expected Factor-Intensity Added (EFA) for Kathmandu = 1.935

TABLE 1
FACTOR INTENSITY

Sno.	Factors	IP	FI
1	Twitter Feeds	0.06	0.27
2	Topography		
2.1	City Plan	0.05	0.225
2.2	Bridges	0.03	0.135
2.3	Dam	0.02	0.09
3	City Plan		
3.1	Hospitals	0.04	0.18
3.2	Schools	0.03	0.135
3.3	Police Stations	0.01	0.045
3.4	Residential	0.06	0.27
3.5	Office	0.01	0.045
3.6	Malls	0.02	0.09
4	Transport		
4.1	Airport	0.03	0.135
4.2	Railways/Metro	0.05	0.225
4.3	Waterways	0.0	0.0
5	Power Plants (Nuclear, Electric, Sewage treatment, Hydroelectric)	0.02	0.09

Sno = Serial number, IP = Impact Probability, FI = Factor Intensity

Damage Score is calculated using the Expected Factor-Intensity Added (EFA) calculated from previous step.

Total Intensity (TI) = $EFA + II$.

Damage Score = $TI * Population\ Density\ (PD)$.^[9]

Damage score of Kathmandu is calculated in Table 2.

TABLE 2
DAMAGE SCORE

Location	II	PD	EFA	TI	DS
Kathmandu	4.5	13,225	1.935	6.435	85102.88

II = Impact Intensity, PD = Population Density, TI = Final Intensity
EFA = Expected Factor Intensity, DS = Damage Score

Table 2 shows the process of calculation of damage score for Kathmandu. Damage score for ten different locations across Nepal is incorporated in Table 3.

TABLE 3
DAMAGE SCORE

Locations	II	PD	EFA	TI	DS
Banepa	4.9	2845.68	0.833	5.733	16314.28
Kathmandu	4.5	13,225	1.935	6.435	85102.88
Sindhupalchowk	5.5	110	0.5225	6.0225	662.475
Dolakha	4.9	85	0.4165	5.3165	451.9025
Pokhara	5	4,798.8	1.5	6.5	31192.2
Rasuwa	5.7	28	0.7505	6.4505	180.614
Gorkha	7.9	80	0.7505	8.6505	692.04
Doti District	3.0	100	0.24	3.24	324
Rammechhap	6.3	130	0.4725	6.7725	880.425
Nuwakot	4.9	250	0.656	5.656	1414

II = Impact Intensity, PD = Population Density, TI = Final Intensity
EFA = Expected Factor Intensity, DS = Damage Score

SPATIAL ANALYSIS AND CLUSTERING

As discussed earlier all the factor data is stored in a spacial format. Each factor data is used to create a map layers. Different map layers represent different factors. Social feeds are used to recognize distressed locations. This data is combined with existing static data (such as topography, building infrastructures, population density etc.) and real time data (such as impact intensity, satellite imagery) to create a layered map. Various libraries in R like ggplot2, ggmap, rgdal, maps and mapdata are used to create this layered map. Various factor data in special format are stored in a dataframe in R. A code snippet for the creating a layered map is given in Fig 2.

```
# loading the required packages
library("ggplot2")
library("ggmap")
library("maptools")
library("rgdal")
library("maps")
library("mapdata")
ogrInfo("C:/Users/saurabh kumar/Pictures/all-damage-nepal-april-28th-2015", "All_Damage_Nepal_Apr
data.mp" <- readShapeSpatial("C:/Users/saurabh kumar/Pictures/all-damage-nepal-april-27th-2015/A
#data.mp <- readShapeSpatial("C:/Users/saurabh kumar/Pictures/StatPlanet_India_Hindi/StatPlanet
#data.shape <- readOGR("C:/Users/saurabh kumar/Pictures/all-damage-nepal-april-28th-2015", "All_I
#plot(data.mp, expand=0.2)
# creating a sample data.frame with your lat/lon points
lon <- c(80.31, 88.5)
lat <- c(90.33, 26.5)
df <- as.data.frame(cbind(lon, lat))
data.mp <- sproj4transform(data.mp, CRS("+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84"))
data.mp <- fortify(data.mp)
# getting the map
mappilbert <- get_map(location = c(lon = mean(df$lon), lat = mean(df$lat)), zoom = 7,
mappilbert <- mappilbert + geom_polygon(aes(x=long, y=lat, group=group), fill="grey", size=2, c
# plotting the map with some points on it
ggmap(mappilbert) +
plot(data.mp, expand=0.2) +
geom_point(data = df, aes(x = lon, y = lat, fill = "red", alpha = 0.8), size = 5, shape = 21) +
# guides(fill=FALSE, alpha=FALSE, size=FALSE)
```

Fig 2: Code Snippet

Fig 3 shows individual layers of Twitter Feeds, Impact Intensity and Population Density. These layers are combined to give a layered map.

Fig 3: Layered Map

The clusters are created using the layered map. These plotted points, in the layered map, will form a large cluster. Divisive Clustering will be performed on the resultant cluster to create smaller clusters. These smaller clusters will in turn be given priorities based on the damage score. The cluster with highest damage score will have the highest priority. Diana function in the cluster package of R will be used for the divisive clustering. Fig 4 shows the formation of Priority Cluster map.

Fig 3: Layered Map

Fig 4: Priority Clusters

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The damage score and priority clusters signify the result of our work. To validate this result, a damage comparison between damage score and actual number of deaths due to earthquake is done.[10] This comparison is shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4
DAMAGE COMPARISON

Location	II	DS	Total Deaths
Kathmandu	4.5	85102.88	1226
Nuwakot	4.9	1414	1109
Gorkha	7.9	692.04	449
Dolakha	4.9	451.9025	177

II = Impact Intensity, DS = Damage Score

The above table shows that Gorkha, having a higher Impact Intensity of 7.9, has lower deaths than Kathmandu and Nuwakot. The Damage Scores for Kathmandu and Nuwakot

are higher than that of Gorkha. This proves our result that the actual damage, total deaths, corresponds to the Damage Score of the location. Therefore Impact Intensity alone should not be taken into consideration in the disaster response and recovery. Our model produces a better result in predicting the actual damage.

CONCLUSION

This paper has established the importance of Data Analytics in disaster response and recovery. It introduced the disaster management techniques and the factors that affect it. A combination of static and real time data has been used to formulate a model for improved disaster response and recovery. This model helps to point out the drawbacks of existing disaster management techniques and helps to identify better techniques. The scope of such a practical model is immense. The model not only aids the rescue teams, but also empowers the local people to help themselves.

Our long term goals are:

- ❖ Once a disaster has struck, one of the main recovery operations is to set up base camps for the misplaced, wounded victims. Our model should do a spatial analysis of resources, topography, impact intensity reports, network routes, population density and generates all the ideal locations for setup of base camps. These camps would be strategically placed so that they are as close as possible to hospitals, police stations, airports etc. Ideally these base camps should be in a low impact region with high availability of resources and in proximity to densely populated area. The geo-locations of these basecamps should be mapped using a Vector GIS.
- ❖ Automate this entire process and make the current model into an encapsulated autonomous system. The system will already contain all static data such as topography, infrastructure etc. for the given region. It will periodically poll the Internet, performing sentiment analysis and

searching for hints of any disasters. On encountering such hints, it will start generating maps, network routes etc. without any human interventions. The system can be considered a neural network in the sense that it learns and grows, thus rectifying previous errors.

- ❖ Include demographics such as age distribution, income range, GDP, crime rate etc. for the region under consideration. Analysis of such demographics would aid in the long term recovery plan.

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